

Severe Preeclampsia Complicated by Subarachnoid Hemorrhage and HELLP Syndrome: Case Report

Azucena Isabel Monge Díaz*¹ (ORCID ID: 0009-0005-1681-8848), Guadalupe Ivette de los Ángeles Salas², Yuselmy Alejandra Santoyo Pérez², David Arturo Moreno Zepeda²

¹Fourth-year Resident in Gynecology and Obstetrics, Facultad de Medicina Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán, Clínica Hospital Mérida, ISSSTE. Calle sin Nombre, Susulá, Yucatán, Mérida, México. CP 97314.

²Gynecology and Obstetrics Service, Facultad de medicina Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán, Clínica Hospital Mérida ISSSTE. Calle sin Nombre, Susulá, Yucatán, Mérida, México. CP 97314.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Severe preeclampsia may progress to major neurological complications and HELLP syndrome (1,2). Subarachnoid hemorrhage (SAH) in this context is rare but associated with high maternal morbidity. Early recognition and multidisciplinary management are essential to improve maternal outcomes.

Case Presentation: A 35-year-old primigravida at 30 weeks of gestation presented to the obstetric emergency department, where a diagnosis of severe preeclampsia was made. A Kerr-type cesarean section was performed due to maternal–fetal deterioration. In the immediate postpartum period, she developed Mississippi Class II HELLP syndrome requiring management in the Obstetric Intensive Care Unit. She subsequently presented with headache and visual disturbances. Head CT revealed diffuse right frontoparietotemporal SAH (Fisher II) with vasogenic edema. Neurosurgical evaluation determined no need for urgent intervention. The patient improved with antihypertensive therapy, neuroprotection, and close monitoring.

Conclusions: SAH may occur as a postpartum complication in patients with preeclampsia/HELLP (7,8). Persistent headache or visual symptoms in these patients should prompt evaluation for intracranial hemorrhage. Multidisciplinary management is essential.

KEYWORDS: severe preeclampsia, HELLP syndrome, subarachnoid hemorrhage, pregnancy.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy remain a leading cause of maternal morbidity and mortality (1). Severe preeclampsia may progress to HELLP syndrome (2). HELLP syndrome is associated with thrombotic microangiopathy and endothelial dysfunction, increasing the risk of serious complications such as acute kidney injury, hepatic hematoma, pulmonary edema, and cerebrovascular events (6). SAH associated with preeclampsia/HELLP is rare but represents a life-threatening emergency; its pathophysiology involves impaired cerebral autoregulation, vasospasm, fibrinoid necrosis, and vascular fragility triggered by hypertensive crises (4). This report describes a case of severe preeclampsia complicated by HELLP syndrome and SAH during the postpartum period.

II. CASE REPORT

A 35-year-old primigravida at 30 weeks of gestation presented with a hypertensive crisis (220/110 mmHg) and organ dysfunction, meeting criteria for severe preeclampsia (1). A Kerr-type cesarean section was performed once the patient was stabilized.

In the immediate postpartum period, she developed Mississippi Class II HELLP syndrome (6). Laboratory tests showed severe thrombocytopenia, elevated AST/ALT and LDH levels, and increased total bilirubin. The laboratory trend analysis allowed visualization of the platelet nadir, hepatic injury peak, and subsequent recovery, consistent with the biphasic evolution of HELLP syndrome described in recent literature (6,7).

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She later developed persistent headache and visual disturbances, prompting neuroimaging evaluation. Non-contrast CT revealed diffuse right frontoparietotemporal SAH, thin component (<1 mm), Fisher grade II, with sulcal effacement due to vasogenic edema and no midline shift or herniation.

A neurosurgical team from a tertiary center evaluated the patient on-site and recommended conservative management, including strict blood pressure control, neurological monitoring, and initiation of nimodipine, along with analgesics, antiemetics, and continuation of antihypertensive therapy. The patient remained hemodynamically stable, with improvement in headache and no focal neurological deficits. She demonstrated full recovery of HELLP parameters and adequate blood pressure control. She was discharged with telmisartan/hydrochlorothiazide 80/12.5 mg PO every 24 hours.

III. DISCUSSION

This case demonstrates the progression from severe preeclampsia to HELLP syndrome and subsequent neurological complication. Pregnancy interruption is the definitive treatment once the mother is stabilized, particularly when there is progressive organ dysfunction or risk to maternal–fetal health, according to ACOG and ISSHP (1). The laboratory pattern observed aligns with the contemporary literature on HELLP syndrome (6,7).

Despite biochemical improvement, neurological symptoms emerged, likely related to persistent endothelial dysfunction and cerebral vasospasm (7,8). The Fisher II SAH suggests a thin hemorrhage with lower risk of severe vasospasm compared to Fisher III–IV, but requiring close monitoring. The 2023 AHA/ASA guidelines for aneurysmal SAH recommend early use of nimodipine to prevent delayed cerebral ischemia secondary to vasospasm, a measure applied in this case (4,5).

Inter-hospital referral networks optimize management in settings with transfer limitations, consistent with recent Latin American literature showing that inter-facility support can mitigate care delays in neurological obstetric emergencies when proper monitoring and blood pressure control are available (8).

IV. CONCLUSION

SAH is a rare but severe complication within the preeclampsia–HELLP spectrum, even in the postpartum period. Laboratory trend interpretation helps anticipate complications and guide clinical decisions. Multidisciplinary management is essential for improving outcomes (1,4,7). Conservative management with strict blood pressure control, nimodipine, and neurosurgical follow-up may be effective in Fisher II SAH without signs of intracranial hypertension or herniation.

This case also underscores the importance of multidisciplinary coordination and clear protocols in second-level hospitals managing neurological obstetric complications.

Fig1

Fig 2

Fig 3

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